

VITICULTURE DEFINITION – WHAT IS VITICULTURE? VITICULTURE IN UZBEK SSR HOW TO GROW GRAPES FOR PROFIT – COMMERCIAL GRAPE GROWER’S ESSENTIAL GUIDE

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Abstract: The article discusses the main properties of grapes and its effects on the human body. A systematic modern review of specialized literature and current scientific data has been carried out.

Key words: grape, health, Central Asian, grapevine.

Viticulture refers to studying and growing grapes, either for wine production or for raw consumption (table grapes). Viticulture includes all the agricultural studies, efforts, and actions of growing grapes until the day of harvest.

On the other hand, Oenology refers to studying and growing grapes, especially for wine production, but also to the complicated process of making wine after harvesting the crop.

According to studies, first grape producers recorded in the Near East during 6.000-8.000 BC. According to Greek mythology, the ancient god Dionysus brought a grapevine from Asia to the Greeks. The first findings of systemic grapevine production in ancient Greece were determined around 4.000 BC. From 2.000 BC, it had already become a vital element of the country's economy. Some people believe that it was transferred from Crete to Sicily -and then- to entire Europe from the 13th century onwards.

In the Central Asian region, Uzbekistan occupies a leading position in the development of viticulture. Over 58% of the area of grape plantings in the region is concentrated here, with a high proportion of table and sultana-raisin varieties. Both of these groups of varieties, taken together, make up about 55% (table varieties - 30.9% and summer varieties - 23.5%). All this, combined with favorable environmental conditions, makes Uzbekistan a leading republic in the production of high-quality new table varieties and the country's main industrial base for the production of dried grape products - sultanas and raisins. This is facilitated by a sufficient amount of active temperatures (over 4000°C), a long growing season (over 220 days), and high temperature during the ripening phase of the crop, which favors intensive sugar accumulation and ensures appropriate commercial qualities of table grapes and dried products. Thus, in

this region, a table, raisin and sultana assortment of grapes has formed and the presence of a large number of valuable varieties in it.

An important advantage of viticulture in the Central Asian region is the absence of phylloxera, which allows you to cultivate your own root crop here. Low water availability due to the lack of rain in the late spring, summer and early autumn periods has determined the irrigated cultivation of grapes. Technical varieties of grapes are also cultivated in the republic, from the harvest of which juices and high-quality vintage dessert wines are prepared.

The main system for maintaining bushes is a vertical four-wire trellis (90%) and a trellis with a canopy. In a number of farms, alleys are arranged on inter-block and intra-block roads. In the Tashkent region, table grape varieties are cultivated on arcs. In the southwestern zone of the republic, individual areas, mainly of sultana varieties, are cultivated "overgrown", the formation of the bushes is large fan or one-sided fan. Due to the great growth force of the bushes, they are given a high load of eyes and yield.

The basis of the assortment of table-raisin and sultana varieties are indigenous varieties belonging to the eastern ecological-geographical group. The most common of them include: Khusayne (3.5 thousand hectares), Taifi pink and Nimrang (4.0 thousand hectares), etc. Of the new varieties of Soviet selection, the most common are: Oktyabrsky, Early VIRA, Gazal Kara, Muscat Uzbek, Rizamat, Jura uzyum, Soviet. Among the group of raisin varieties, the most common are Black raisin (11 thousand hectares), the harvest of which is used for drying and fresh consumption, as well as White raisin (5 thousand hectares). Small areas are occupied by the pink Kishmish and Askeri varieties.

In recent years, new seedless varieties have been developed: Kishmish Khishrau, Kishmish VIRA, Yangier, Kishmish Zarafshan, and the Perlet variety has been introduced. The group of early ripening varieties has been replenished with the following varieties: Ertaspar, Vasari, Early Schroeder.

Of the technical varieties, the largest areas are occupied by varieties: Bayan Shirey, Kuldzhinsky, Saperavi, Rkatsiteli, etc.

Scientific research on viticulture is carried out at the Research and Production Association for Fruit Growing, Viticulture and Winemaking named after R.R. Schroeder and at the Department of Viticulture of the Tashkent Agricultural Institute.

Grape production—if done rationally and on a scalable basis—can be a good source of long term income. However, vine growing, either for raw consumption ([table grapes](#)) or winemaking, is a choice that will "tie" you and your land up for

at least two decades. Thus, this decision requires extensive research and a clear business plan.

First of all, you have to know that many countries have very strict regulations about giving licenses for grapevine growing. Secondly, it is always better to have your own land (at least 4-5 hectares), because growing grapes requires many years of field exploitation. The average vine plant matures and gives the maximum yield about 7-8 years after planting. Thus, if you consider renting a field, fixed costs will increase, and no one can assure you that you will be able to occupy this field a decade from now.

In a few words, the vine is a perennial plant, with a great variety of growing techniques. As a general rule, winemaking varieties mature and give a good yield about 7-8 years after planting. On the other hand, contemporary table grapes varieties (intended for raw consumption of grapes) can reach their maturity and give the maximum yield just two years after planting. They can continue to give a good yield for about 15-17 years, and then most table grapes producers plow and destroy the crop because it cannot give a good yield anymore.

Most commercial grape growers start the vine from grafted plants. However, in some countries that the soil is free from phylloxera, they may prefer autogenous plants. It is important not to plant a new vineyard in the same place an old one has been recently removed. The soil there will most probably be depleted and possibly infected. The time window between replanting can be 2-5 years (ask a local licensed agronomist). Variety selection is very crucial. Each vine variety has unique quality characteristics that can be expressed only under specific climate and soil conditions and growing techniques.

Variety selection is a restrictive factor when growing grapes. The rootstock and scion varieties should be consistent and -of course- choosing the proper variety for your climate is crucial. In general, vines prefer warm and dry summers and cold winters (not frosty), soils with less than 25% clay content and a small percentage in gravel content, although these depend again on the rootstock variety. Sufficient amounts of organic matter are also required. High humidity levels during the summer will most probably increase fungal infections. Temperatures lower than $-3\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ ($27\text{ }^{\circ}\text{F}$) during spring or lower than $-15\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ ($5\text{ }^{\circ}\text{F}$) during the dormancy period will cause damage on wood, young shoots, and buds. In addition, soil temperatures should be over $5\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ ($41\text{ }^{\circ}\text{F}$) in order for the vine to reclaim in maximum the soil organic matter. Optimum pH and RH levels depend on the variety. Generally, optimum pH levels are between

6,5 and 7,5. However, there are varieties that grow well in levels close to 4,5 or even 8,5.

Once you have done with all the bureaucracy and variety selection, you have to start the pre-planning processes. Vine producers till the land at that time and remove any previous crop remains. However, very heavy tillage in the inclined ground may have unpleasant consequences, such as erosion. Extremely inclined fields need to be leveled. If not, water will most probably rinse from upper levels and gather in lower levels, causing waterlogged conditions.

Next, producers install the drip irrigation system, when it comes to irrigated vineyards. When they are ready for transplanting, they make small holes in the ground, where they plant the seedlings. Fertilization, Drip Irrigation, and Weed Management are applied in most cases.

After transplanting, it is time to apply the shape and training method of the vine. There are several training systems to choose from, depending on the vine variety, environmental and soil conditions, harvesting techniques, and of course, the experience of each grape farmer. Producers give the wanted shape on their vines using support and pruning. This procedure in most cases requires 2-3 years in winemaking varieties and 1-2 year in table grapes varieties

Once they have performed trellis implementation and shaping, they start the annual work schedule, which includes pruning, deadheading, defoliation, and grape thinning. Some grape growers remove most of the developing sprouts, during the whole growing period, in order to encourage the plant to devote its resources in fewer but higher in quality fruits. Of course, this method is not preferred by all grape growers.

It is crucial to monitor the crop almost daily during the growing season in order to prevent the spread of diseases and other negative circumstances. Harvesting can be made manually, using scissors or knives, or mechanically by harvesting tractors. However, table grapes can only be harvested manually. Each method has its pros and cons. Traditional vineyards in Europe that produce wines of high-quality and low quantity yield are harvested manually.

Grape harvesting time is difficult to be generalized. It is a combination of variety together with climate conditions, soil characteristics, and growing techniques. Rarely can we harvest grapes the same date we harvested the previous year. Even on the same farm, with the same vine varieties, harvesting time of vines may differ. Generally, we could say that in the northern hemisphere, most varieties mature from August to November, while in the southern hemisphere from March to August. After harvesting, grape growers

carefully separate healthy grapes from diseased, clean them carefully, and either cool and store them in order to be sold raw or start the winemaking procedure. After harvesting and foliage drop, the vine starts to enter the dormancy period periodically.

As far as yield is concerned, in general, when we harvest table grape varieties, we can harvest a bigger yield than when we grow wine varieties. But even among wine varieties, there are great differences in yield. Every farmer has to make informed and fact-based decisions and find the proper balance between quantity and quality. Some European grape producers ([Sauvignon](#) or Cabernet varieties) claim that they don't want to harvest more than 6 tons of grapes per hectare, because a higher yield will dramatically decrease the product quality. Although this yield may seem incredibly low compared to other varieties, it is more than enough to financially support the producer, because the product can be marketed at a premium price. On the other hand, medium and low-quality winemaking varieties can give 20-40 tons per hectare or even more, but they cannot be marketed at a high price. Table grape varieties can give a yield of 20-50 tons per hectare.

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